

HERBAL FACE PACK FOR GLOWING SKIN: Development and Assessment

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Abstract:

Herbal face pack is made by using singhara powder, pomelo fruit powder, neem powder, sandal wood powder, aloe vera powder, turmeric, multani mitti, and licorice. The main ingredients in this face pack is singhara and pomelo powder as well as the multani mitti. Singhara detoxify and cleanse the face following a glowing skin. Pomelo fruit powder nourishes the skin and guards against dryness, acne, wrinkles, also shows skin softening effect as well as make the skin complexion clear. Multani mitti brightens skin tone, eliminates tanning and sunburns, cleans pores, evens up facial skin tone, and creates adorably smooth skin. In Ayurveda, the herbal paste is known as “mukha lepa” (Face pack) used for as a facial therapy. This herbal paste is applied to the face to cure pigmentation, scars, markings, and acne. The smooth powder that is applied to the face is called a face pack. The herbal face pack promotes blood circulation, keeps the skin's elasticity and tightness, and also cleans the skin of filth. The prepared face pack is assessed using a variety of evaluation criteria, including washability, stability tests, photochemical assessment, physico-chemical, organoleptic evaluation, rheological and antimicrobial evaluation. Thus, in the current work, we discovered that the face packs had good properties, and additional optimization studies are needed on this study to discover the useful advantages of face packs for human usage as a cosmetic product.

Keywords: Singhara, Pomelo, Multani mitti, tanning, sunburn

1. INTRODUCTION

Cosmetics are readily available commercial goods that are used to enhance the skin's look through washing, beautifying and attractiveness promotion.¹ Cosmetics have a long history that dates back at least 7000 years. Since the time of Ayurveda, herbal products have been utilized for cosmetic reasons², they improve or alter the way the face looks, the body smells, or the texture of the skin.

Herbal face packs are used to open up pores on the skin, maintain the flexibility of the skin, and increase blood flow.³ Women who have wrinkles, dark bags under their eyes, pimples, or acne can get rid of them with the aid of the Ayurveda face packs. The fairness and smoothness of the skin are improved by herbal face packs. By applying herbal face packs in accordance with our skin type, we can maximize their benefits. These face packs improve skin radiance and are the greatest Ayurveda remedy for boosting fairness. One of the oldest and most elegant ways to cleanse the skin is with face packs.⁴

The health and radiance of the skin depend on crucial vitamins, which are abundant in face packs made of natural ingredients. There are numerous ways in which these chemicals have been shown to benefit skin. Utilizing natural face packs is simple. They improve the flow of blood through the veins on the face, which makes the skin appear more vibrant. A good herbal face pack must give the skin the nutrients it needs, which are available as a free-flowing powder. Applied to one's face for exterior use. To give the needed nutrients, it should deeply penetrate the subcutaneous tissues. Each type of skin has unique requirements for the skin pack. For dry, normal, and oily skin types, separate types of packs are now offered. To improve the fairness and smoothness of the skin, face packs are used. It lessens facial imperfections like wrinkles, acne, and dark under-eye circles.⁵

Face packs are essentially supplements that offer extra advantages. For various types of skin, several herbal face packs are employed. Herbal face packs can assist with the appearance of wrinkles, acne, and dark under-eye circles.⁶ Boost the skin's fairness and smoothness as well. Additionally, it helps someone gain more self-confidence. The most practical and effective method for reaching this goal is Ayurveda.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The current's ingredients were bought from a nearby market and ground up for usage. Details of the some of the plants materials that were utilized to make the face pack are provided below.

Table 1: List of ingredients with their medicinal use

Sl.No.	Name	Figure	Medicinal use
1.	Singhara (<i>Trapa natans</i> L.)		Singhara possess antioxidants like polyphenols and flavonoids powers them to become an anti-oxidant, antibacterial and anti-inflammatory. It also act as a natural detox and cleanse the body of all toxins, rewarding one with glowing skin. ⁷

2.	Pomelo (<i>Citrus maxima</i>)		Vitamins A and C included in pomelo peel keep the skin nourished and guard against dryness, acne, wrinkles, and psoriasis. ⁸
3.	Neem (<i>Azadirachta indica</i>)		Neem is anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, and very helpful for skin that is greasy and prone to acne. The antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and anti-oxidant properties of several chemical components cause an anti-acne effect. Acne treatment is one of neem's most well-known skin advantages. ⁹
4.	Sandal wood (<i>Santalum alba</i>)		Sandalwood provides anti-aging and anti-tanning benefits. Sandalwood keeps the skin cool, fair, and healthy while protecting it from the damaging effects of environmental pollutants. Sandalwood is advantageous Antimicrobial Ayurvedic herbs are used to treat scars and a variety of skin conditions. ¹⁰
5.	Aloe Vera (<i>Aloe barbadensis</i>)		Aloe vera contains anti-microbial properties, making it the perfect solution for treating acne and pimples. For skin, aloe vera is a fantastic moisturiser. Several nutrients, including glycerin, sodium palmate, sodium carbonate, sodium palm kemelate, and sorbitol, are present in aloe vera powder. ¹¹
6.	Turmeric powder (<i>Curuma longa</i>)		The major purpose of turmeric is to revitalise the skin. In addition to having antibacterial, antimicrobial, and anti-inflammatory qualities, it delays the appearance of wrinkles. It is ideal source of the blood cleaner. Due to its antiseptic and antibacterial characteristics, which combat zits and breakouts to give your skin a youthful look, it is useful in treating acne. It also lessens the sebaceous glands' production of oil. ¹²

7.	Multani mitti (Calcium bentonite)		Multani mitti benefits skin in a variety of ways, including reducing pore size, eliminating blackheads and whiteheads, fading freckles, relieving sunburns, washing skin, enhancing blood circulation, boosting complexion, and giving skin a glowing appearance. ¹³
8.	Licorice (Glycyrrhiza glabra)		Licorice shields your skin from the sun's harmful rays, aids in the treatment of acne, lightens dark spots and other skin conditions. ¹⁴

Table 2: Formulation of Herbal Face Pack

Ingredients	Quantity of sample for 100g		
	F1	F2	F3
Singhara	25	23	20
Pomelo	10	10	12
Neem	12	10	08
Sandal wood	22	20	25
Aloe Vera	05	08	07
Turmeric	09	10	08
Multani mitti	12	12	09
Licorice	05	07	08

PROCEDURE:

Three distinct formulations were created using different amounts of each of the F1 to F3 components. In **Table 2**, each ingredient's concentration was listed. Using sieve #120, the precise amount of components was weighed and processed into a fine powder. Then to ensure consistent mixing, all materials were geometrically combined using the serial dilution method. The finished face pack was then placed within a self-sealing polyethylene bag, labelled, and used for subsequent investigation.¹⁵

Procedure of face pack application:

Take the face pack powder that has been developed and place it in a bowl with the necessary amount of rose water. After thoroughly blending, apply to the facial skin. Include coverage for spots with acne and pimples. For around 10 to 20 minutes, leave the pack on the face to dry completely and the wash your face with cold water.

Image 1: Formulation of herbal face pack

3. EVALUATIONS OF FORMULATIONS

Following evaluation parameters were performed to ensure superiority of prepared face pack.

3.1 Organoleptic Evaluation:

The organoleptic parameters include its nature, odor, color, appearance and texture which were evaluated manually for its physical properties.¹⁶

3.2 Physical Evaluation:

The microscope approach was used to measure the particle size. By measuring bulk density and tapped density using the Tapping Method, Angle of Repose by funnel method, and bulk density of the dried powder in mixed form, the flow property was assessed.¹⁷

3.3 Physicochemical Evaluation:

Ash content measurements were made using an incinerator, pH was determined using a pH meter, and loss on drying measurements were also made.

3.4 Determination of moisture content:

1.5 g of the drug's powder should be measured into a porcelain dish that is flat and thin. Dry in the oven at 100°C or 105°C, checking that two subsequent weighing's are within 0.5 mg of one another. Desiccate and weigh after cooling. The weight loss is typically noted as moisture.¹⁸

3.5 Irritancy test:

Mark a 1-square-centimeter area on the left dorsal surface. A specific amount of prepared face packs were applied to the designated region, and the application time was recorded. Irritability, erythema, and edema were monitored for regular intervals up to 24 hours and reported if present.¹⁹

3.6 Stability studies:

By keeping the created formulation at various temperatures for a month, stability testing was done on it. The packed glass vials of the formulation were assessed for physical characteristics such color, aroma, pH, consistency, and feel while being stored at different temperatures, including room temperature and 40°C.²⁰

3.7 Microbial assay:

The modified agar well diffusion method was used to assess the antibacterial activity of various formulations. In this procedure, 24 hour broth cultures of *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Streptococcus* the causal organisms for acne vulgaris, were seeded onto nutrient agar plates. We left the agar plates to set up. In order to create evenly spaced wells in each of the plates, a sterile 8 mm borer was used. Herbal extract formulations with 0.5 ml each were randomly added to the wells. The plates were incubated for 24 hours at 37°C. The zones of inhibition (measured in mm) were used to assess the antibacterial activity.²¹

4. Results and Discussion:

4.1 Organoleptic Evaluation

Face pack was prepared and evaluated for organoleptic parameters showed in the **Table 3**. Free-flowing characteristics could be seen in the flow property parameter. The formulation was a pale yellow color. As cosmetic compositions, the aroma of the finished products was well-tolerated and appealing. Smoothness and Texture were acceptable and desirable for cosmetic compositions.

Table 3: Organoleptic Evaluation

SL. No.	Parameters	Observation		
		F1	F2	F3
1	Nature	Powder	Powder	Powder
2	Odor	Slight	Slight	Slight
3	Color	Brown	Brown	Brown
4	Appearance	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth
5	Texture	fine	fine	fine

4.2 Physical Evaluation and Physicochemical Evaluation

The particle size of formulations was in the range of 25-33 µm. The pH of formulation lied near to neutral. The ash content and moisture content was within limit.

Table 4: Physical Parameter and Physicochemical Evaluation

SL. No.	Evaluation parameters	Observation		
		F1	F2	F3
1	Particle size	29-33 µm	25-30 µm	27-31 µm
2	Angle of Repose	35.14	22.816	21.4
3	Bulk density	1.11	3.75	1.09
4	Tapped density	1.28	1.41	1.28
5	Washability	yes	yes	yes
6	Total Ash	0.90	1.35	1.81
7	Water soluble Ash	9.5	8	13.5
8	Acid insoluble ash	21.5	22	34
9	pH	6.06	6.09	6.08
10	Moisture Content	1.8% w/w	1.5% w/w	1.9% w/w

4.3 Irritancy Test

The results of irritancy test were shown in **Table 5**. The formulation showed no irritation, redness, edema and Inflammation during irritancy studies. This formulation is safe to use for skin

Table 5: Irritancy Test

SL.No.	Parameters	Observation		
		F1	F2	F3
1	Irritant	No Irritation	No Irritation	No Irritation
2	Erythema	No Irritation	No Irritation	No Irritation
3	Edema	No Irritation	No Irritation	No Irritation

4.4 Stability studies

The stability analyses revealed that the formulation's pH changed somewhat while being stored at 40°C, but that no changes were seen at ambient temperature or at 35°C. The additional stability criteria that were discussed and displayed in **Table 6** did not result in any changes to color or odor.

Table 6: Parameters of Stability studies of Formulations

SL.No	Parameters	Observation		
		Room Temp.	35±0.5 ⁰ C	40±0.5 ⁰ C
1	Color	No change	No change	No change
2	Odor	No change	No change	No change
3	pH	6.06 ± 0.11	6.07 ± 0.12	6.09 ± 0.10
4	Texture	Fine	Fine	Fine
5	Appearance	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth

4.5 Antimicrobial evaluation

Table 7: The zone of inhibition diameters of the prepared herbal face pack

Sl. No.	Samples	F1	F2	F3	Control
01	<i>B. subtilis</i>	11mm	08mm	08mm	R
02	<i>Streptococcus</i>	12mm	09mm	07mm	R
03	<i>E-coli</i>	08mm	08mm	14mm	R
04	<i>Klebsiella</i>	14mm	16mm	16mm	R

Note: R= Resistant

Figure 1: Zone of inhibition diameters of prepared herbal face pack (F1, F2, and F3)

Image 2: A- Before application of face pack

B- After application of face pack

5. CONCLUSION

People today require treatments for a variety of skin issues without adverse effects. The use of herbal substances made it possible to create cosmetics that had no negative side effects. Herbal face packs are regarded as a dependable and effective technique to improve skin appearance. The formulation of an herbal face pack using readily available ingredients like Singhara, multani mitti, turmeric, aloe vera, sandalwood, pomelo, neem, and licorice is a really nice attempt in the current study. It is hypothesized that the created formulation had the properties of a typical cosmeceuticals formulation for skincare and was physically, chemically, and microbiologically stable.

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ETHICS APPROVAL AND CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE

Not applicable.

HUMAN AND ANIMAL RIGHTS

No Animals/Humans were used for studies that are base of this research.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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